

EFFECT TO MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF IRON WHISKER
BY NEUTRON DAMAGE

Dr. A. Okura

Institute of Industrial Science
University of Tokyo

22-1, Roppongi 7 chome Minato-ku
Tokyo 106, Japan

The mechanical properties of iron whisker is common knowledge for it have sharp upper yield point and high value on upper yield stress, this cause is thought for the iron whisker have nearly perfect crystal structure.

Therefore, iron whisker is fit for studies of mechanical properties, and it is require for development of composite materials.

This report is represented on the effect of neutron irradiation and post-irradiation annealing on mechanical properties of iron whisker.

Iron whisker produced by hydrogen reduction of liquid iron halide salt were irradiated to a fission neutron dose of 1.94×10^{16} n/cm (> 1.28 MeV) at $19 \pm 1^\circ\text{K}$, and isochronally annealed at the range 200°C to 500°C .

Mechanical properties of iron whisker has been investigated by Instron Machine at -196°C .

Neutron irradiation was found to cause a softening effect on iron whisker, and upper yield stress remained unchanged on annealing up to 330°C and then recovered steadily untill it returned to unirradiated value at 500°C .

On the basis of present study it is suggested that irradiation softening of iron whisker is found on aggregation point diffects such as dislocation loop.

Introduction

Generally, the effect to mechanical property of metallic materials with neutron irradiation is reported to show in high Yung's ratio, high value of upper yield stress and increase of hardness, the other, a section contraction ratio and strain is decreased (1). But the latest studies is reported on the softening phenomenon with irradiation of the iron whisker (2) and the pure iron (3).

This work is investigation on the change of electrical resistance by neutron damage, effect on the tensile structure for the formation of crystal defect and the recovery of crystal defect by annealing.

Experimental Apparatus and Method

1. Production of Whisker

Iron whisker is produced by hydrogen reduction of $\text{FeCl}_2 \cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (iron halid solt), the growth orientation of whisker is shown $\langle 100 \rangle$ result of X-ray analysis, and the sectional structure is shown the square, the purity of whisker is indicated 99.99%.

The production apparatus of whisker is shown Fig.1.

Fig.1 Production apparatus of iron whisker.

2. Neutron Irradiation Apparatus

Neutron irradiation to the iron whisker have been the low temperature apparatus at Kyoto University Reactor (KUR) and Rikyo University Reactor (TRIGA II type), the irradiation condition is shown table 1.

The irradiation sample under the condition I and II is used to tensile strength test, change of the electrical resistance during neutron irradiation were measurements under the condition III.

Table 1 Neutron Irradiation Condition

Conditions	I	II	III
Reactors	TRIGA II type	KUR	KUR
Power	0.1 Mw	5 Mw	5 Mw
Neutron energy	0.2 Mev < En < 1 Mev	En > 1.28 Mev	En > 1.28 Mev
Temperature	70°C	-196°C	-196°C
Time	260 hr	49 hr	77 hr
Flux	$2.0 \times 10^{12} / \text{cm}^2 \cdot \text{s}$	$1.1 \times 10^{11} / \text{cm}^2 \cdot \text{s}$	$1.2 \times 10^{11} / \text{cm}^2 \cdot \text{s}$
Irradiation Volume	$1.9 \times 10^{18} / \text{cm}^2 \cdot \text{s}$	$1.8 \times 10^{16} / \text{cm}^2 \cdot \text{s}$	$3.3 \times 10^{16} / \text{cm}^2 \cdot \text{s}$

3. Measurement of Electrical Resistance and the Method

Electrical resistance is measured by potentiometer method at the condition of low temperature (-196°C), and the electric current of measurement base is 10 mA.

Electrical resistance is measured on the iron whisker of different diameter which has growth orientation <100>, <110> for investigation of the radius effect.

Resistance of Cu wire which jointed the sample is measured with the potentiometer before experiment, and total resistance value was revised. The change of electrical resistance during the cooling from room temperature to -196°C before irradiation and it after irradiation to room temperature is measured.

The irradiation sample were preserve in liquid nitrogen and it used the test, mechanical property of iron whisker have been investigation by Instron Machine.

Iron whisker is holded the chuck with binding agent, the length of iron whisker and the diameter is measured at magnification 600 by a microscope.

The length of whisker for measurement is usually the constant in 2 mm (the length between a chuck and chuck), and the tensile strain rate is 0.4 mm per min., the test temperature is all -196°C.

The sample after seting is steeped in liquid nitrogen bus, and the tensile strain test of iron whisker have been in liquid nitrogen bus.

The pen of the recorder could follow the stress change when the stress increased, but not sufficiently follow abrupt stress drops.

Experimental Results

1. The Change of Electrical Resistance with Neutron Irradiation

Relation between irradiation volume ϕ_t and electrical resistance ρ when the neutron irradiation at low temperature -196°C is shown Fig.2.

Definite point of experimental results is as follow.

1) Electrical resistance ρ is changed large to compare between the early time of the irradiation ($\phi_t < 0.1 \times 10^{16} \text{ n/cm}^2$) and parst any time of irradiation ($\phi_t \geq 0.1 \times 10^{16} \text{ n/cm}^2$). (See Fig.2-(a))

Where, $\Delta\rho$ is shown the volume of crystal defect which occur by the neutron irradiation.

2) The slope of the straight line at condition $\phi_t > 0.1 \times 10^{16} \text{ n/cm}^2$ which show Fig.2-(b) is not the dependence to the diameter of iron whisker, but the

Fig.2 Change of electrical resistance with fast neutron at 19°C

growth orientation $\langle 110 \rangle$ as compare with $\langle 100 \rangle$ is show the large variance, that is, large value of the ratio $(d\Delta\rho/d\phi_t)$ at the growth orientation $\langle 110 \rangle$ is means easely the formation of crystal defect by neutron irradiation.

3) A value on y-axis in Fig.2-(a) is dependence to a diameter of whisker, that is, the residual electrical resistance at the low temperature (-196 °C) and irradiation volume ($\phi_t = 0$) is means dependence to diameter of whisker.

The increase volume ($\Delta\rho$) of resistance with the irradiation can be thought the volume of Flenkel's defect, and it is common knowledge that the number of defect is proportion to the change of electrical resistance, where the Flenkel's defect of 1 atom % is suppose increase volume of resistance ρ_F , and the concentration of defect C_F is as follow

$$C_F = \Delta\rho/\rho_F \quad (1)$$

Except the carbon, generally it is asceration by Alfred's that the concentration of defect in metals is not dependence on the increase resistance ρ_F , consequently the changing ratio $(d\Delta\rho/d\phi_t)$ is means the formation velocity of crystal defect inner iron whisker.

Relation between the increase volume of resistance $\Delta\rho$ by irradiation and the changing ratio $(d\Delta\rho/d\phi_t)$ is shown Table 2, where I is shown the range $\phi_t < 0.1 \times 10^{16} \text{ n/cm}^2$, II is shown the range $\phi_t > 0.1 \times 10^{16} \text{ n/cm}^2$, I_{ave} is shown average of changing ratio.

Table 2 Value of $\Delta\rho$ and $d\Delta\rho/d\phi_t$ calculated from Fig.4

diameter d(μ) orientation		16.5 <100>	80.1 <100>	68.6 <110>
$\Delta\rho$ ($\times 10^{-8} \Omega \cdot \text{cm}$)	$\Delta\rho_I$	0.55	0.91	0.93
	$\Delta\rho_{II}$	1.88	1.87	3.28
	$\Delta\rho_{Total}$	2.43	2.77	4.21
$d\Delta\rho/d\phi$ ($\times 10^{-24} \Omega \cdot \text{cm}$)	$d\Delta\rho/d\phi_{tI_{ave}}$	5.47	9.05	9.30
	$d\Delta\rho/d\phi_{tII}$	0.60	0.59	1.04

Fig.3 Temperature dependency of resistivity for iron whisker $\langle 100 \rangle$

Fig.4 Temperature dependency of resistivity for iron whisker $\langle 110 \rangle$

2. Recovery of Irradiation Defect

The change of electrical resistance to temperature after irradiation is shown Fig.3 ~ Fig.4.

The crystal defect inner whisker occur with irradiation is moved at the each inherency temperature in proportion up to temperature, and it is disappear, electrical resistance is recovered, and it is thought that the electrical resistance is agree initial resistance, but experimental results is shown the difference a small quantity to initial resistance value.

The cause of defect inner iron whisker could be conceivable the impurity, vacancy inner whisker, the oxidized film and micro crack on surface of whisker. The increase of whisker volume and surface area by increase diameter of whisker could be thought the effect to residual electrical resistance. Effect size on residual resistivity of whisker at -196°C is shown Fig.5.

Fig.5 Effect of size on residual resistivity of iron whisker at 19°K

3. Results of Tensile Test

The whisker which had neutron irradiation at low temperature (-196°C) has been the annealing at the each temperature range from room temperature untill to 500°C , and has been tensile test in liquid nitrogen bus.

Most sample for tensile test was the growth orientation $\langle 100 \rangle$, where S is sectional area of whisker, d is a diameter of whisker, σ_{el} , ϵ_{el} is limite value of the proportion which obtain from stress-strain curve, σ_{uy} , ϵ_{uy} is shown the value of strain and stress at upper yield point, $\sigma_{el}/\epsilon_{el}$ is appearance Yang ratio, $\dot{\epsilon}$ is strain rate.

Upper yield stress (σ_{uy}) of iron whisker is nown generally it have inverse proportion to areciprocal number of sectional area of sample, the discussion on these point after annealing is as follow. These results is shown Fig.6 ~ Fig.7.

Fig.6 Relation between upper yield stress and reciprocal of cross area

Fig.7 Relation between upper yield stress and reciprocal of cross area

Both on un-irradiation sample and irradiation sample is shown similar a tendency to.

Sher structure of iron whisker must be shown by equation $G/2\pi$ (G :shear modulus) if it is perfect crystal and it have near value to the theoretical structure, but the results is shown a fairly low value.

The tensile structure of whisker is changed with the size, this result gave suggestions with regard to the whisker have any defect distribution.

A few defect in whisker is means the work for source of dislocation before the reach to upper yield point, for example, the slope of strain-stress curve before the reach to upper yield point is shown small value than estimate value which carculated from Yang's ratio (6).

These results is shown that the whisker have defect for during growth, and this defect gave the effect to the structure of whisker.

Main defect inner the whisker is thought the impurity and the vacancy inner whisker which has interact for source of dislocation. Another component, carbon, nitrogen inner whisker is controlled the action of moving dislocation, oxidized film on surface whisker is infrence for the occure micro crack.

These defect is change with the diameter of whisker, and the yield stress of whisker can be thought proportion in a reciprocal number of sectional area of sample.

An average value of upper yield stress at whisker of any diameter could be calculation from previous relation

$$\sigma_{uy} = a/s + b \quad (2)$$

Calculation results on a and b used the method of least squares is shown Table 3.

Table 3 Value of a and b at the differential condition of annealing Temperature

annealing condition		a ($\times 10^{-2}$ kg)	b (kg/mm ²)
A	unirr.	2.4	48
B	R.T. 30 min	1.4	54
C	R.T., 1hr	1.5	45
D	200°C, 2hr	1.2	66
E	330°C, 2hr	1.4	51
F	400°C, 2hr	1.9	63
G	500°C, 2hr	2.1	56

Relation between σ_{uy} and S^{-1} which used the value of a and b in Table 4 is shown Fig.8, the slope of straight line in Fig.8 is shown a sudden change, and it is approach to value of un-irradiation whisker proportion up to annealing temperature.

Relation between σ_{uy} and S is shown Fig.9.

Fig.8 Relation between upper yield stress and reciprocal of cross area

Fig.9 Relation between average value of upper yield stress and cross area of iron whisker which had annealing after neutron irradiation

Upper yield stress of whisker is a sudden decrease with increase of sectional area of sample at condition less than $S = 4 \times 10^{-4} \text{mm}^2$ ($d \approx 20\mu$), therefore, upper yield stress σ_{uy} is constant at the value more than $S = 10 \times 10^{-4} \text{mm}^2$ ($d \approx 33\mu$), this value could be conjecture same value on upper yield stress of iron single crystal.

It have discussion on the softening phenomenon by irradiation and recovery.

The relation between annealing temperature of iron whisker which has any diameter after irradiation and upper yield stress is shown Fig.10, upper yield stress of iron whisker in Fig.10 is changed about 350°C, and the ratio of increase tensile structure is shown large value become smaller diameter of whisker.

Fig.10 Relation between upper stress and annealing temperature

The phenomenon of irradiation softening are thought for the formation of secondary defect at the recovery process of irradiation defect.

Eyre's is observation the dislocation loop of atomic type inner α Fe after irradiation, and it is convinced dislocation loop of $b = a/2\langle 111 \rangle$ on the crystal plane (100) of disunion type lattice (7), (8), this dislocation loop is include the seam defect which have high energy, according, it is moved to toward $\langle 110 \rangle$ or $\langle 100 \rangle$, and it is movement to dislocation loop which unincluded the seam defect as follow equation

Equation (4) is necessity high energy than equation (3), according, the formation of dislocation loop $a \langle 010 \rangle$ is necessity the prescription or irradiation at high temperature, this results is shown fine coincidence with experimental results by Eyre's companion.

Whisker which have a few the grain boundary or dislocation is easy formation of the vacancy or defect at lower irradiation value, and phenomena of irradiation softening could be illustrate for increase of mobility dislocation density by secondary defect.

Conclusion

Investigated results on the relation between the change of electrical resistance and the formation of crystal defect inner whisker by neutron irradiation, and measurement results on the tensile strength after irradiation is shown as follow.

- 1) The formation velocity of crystal defect is dependence the crystal orientation, and it have the relation on the energy for spring out of atom.
 - 2) The formation velocity of crystal defect is shown large value at first time of irradiation, this result could be thought the change of crystal defect concentration.
 - 3) The increase of whisker volume, the increase of surface area on whisker could be considered the effect to residual resistance.
 - 4) Decrease of upper yield stress by irradiation of whisker was recovery to almost before irradiation at annealing temperature 400°C.
- The softing by irradiation and recovery could be thought for disappear and secondary defect which arise at recovery process of the defect.

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